

Prevalence of Depression among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus and its factors affecting the Glycemic control at a Tertiary care Hospital – A Cross Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Depression in Diabetic patients is a significant issue that should be addressed since it can affect both physical and mental health of an individual, Constant monitoring of blood sugar levels, adhering to medications and following a strict diet can put an immense burden on the individual, which worsen his mental and eventually affects his diabetic control in several ways. Nearly every 30% of a Diabetic person tends go under depression, which is often remain undiagnosed, it is important for a person with diabetes to have a strong supportive system. **Objectives:** To assess the association between depression severity and various demographic, clinical, and behavioural factors in patients with type 2 diabetes. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 diabetic patients at Bangalore Baptist Hospital. Depression levels were assessed using the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9). The medication adherence of the participants was assessed using Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8) and Participants were stratified based on demographic and clinical variables, and statistical significance was evaluated using chi-square tests. **Results:** Among the 100 participants, 39% exhibited moderate to severe depression (PHQ > 9). Depression was significantly more prevalent among males (45.5%) than females (25.7%) ($p = 0.04$), and among participants with a monthly income below ₹20,000 (66.7%) compared to higher earners ($p = 0.001$). Daily wage workers (66.7%) and rural residents (62.0%) were also significantly more affected ($p = 0.004$ and $p = 0.002$, respectively). Single, widowed, or divorced individuals had a higher prevalence of depression (60%) compared to married individuals ($p = 0.03$). Clinical factors such as diabetes duration >5 years (46.5%; $p = 0.01$), poor glycemic control (HbA1C > 8.0%; 56.5%, $p = 0.008$), and poor medication adherence (57.7%; $p = 0.002$) showed strong associations with depression. Additionally, current smoking or alcohol use was significantly linked to higher PHQ scores (54.6%; $p = 0.02$). These findings highlight key socio-clinical predictors of depression in diabetic patients. **Conclusion:** Depression in diabetes is significantly influenced by socioeconomic status, clinical severity, and health behaviours. Integrated screening and tailored interventions for mental health should be considered in the management of diabetic patients, especially among high-risk subgroups.

Keywords: Depression, Diabetes Mellitus, PHQ-9, MMAS-8, HbA1C, Socioeconomic factors

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic, progressive, metabolic illness and superimposed depression further debilitates the overall health related quality of life and life expectancy of these individuals. Almost half of the study participants in this survey were anxious and depressed. The associated factors included female gender, longer duration of diabetes, non-insulin treatment, complications including neuropathy, nephropathy, and foot ulcers, and admission due to infected foot ulcers, HHS, and hypoglycaemic coma. The International Diabetes Federation (IDF) has

released new figures showing that 537 million adults are now living with diabetes worldwide a rise of 16% (74 million) since the previous IDF estimates in 2019. International Diabetes Federation (IDF) projections show that by 2045, 783 million adults will be living with diabetes or one in eight adults. This would be an increase of 46%, more than double the estimated population growth (20%) over the same period(1,2).

DM has several categories, including type 1, type 2, maturity-onset diabetes of the young (MODY), gestational diabetes, neonatal diabetes, and secondary causes due to endocrinopathies, steroid use, etc. The

main subtypes of DM are Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) and Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), which classically result from defective insulin secretion (T1DM) and/or action (T2DM). T1DM presents in children or adolescents, while T2DM is thought to affect middle-aged and older adults who have prolonged hyperglycaemia due to poor lifestyle and dietary choices. The pathogenesis for T1DM and T2DM is drastically different and therefore each type has various etiology, presentations, and treatments(3).

Depressive disorder (also known as depression) is a common mental disorder. It involves a depressed mood or loss of pleasure or interest in activities for long periods of time. Depression is different from regular mood changes and feelings about everyday life. It can affect all aspects of life, including relationships with family, friends and community. It can result from or lead to problems at school and at work. Depression can happen to anyone. People who have lived through abuse, severe losses or other stressful events are more likely to develop depression. Women are more likely to have depression than men(4).

According to the ICD-10 classification of the World Health Organization, depressive symptoms can be assigned to different categories of mental disorder, Main symptoms (depressed mood, loss of interest and enjoyment and diminished activity) other symptoms (reduced concentration and attention, reduced self-esteem and self-confidence, feeling guilty and worthless, bleak and pessimistic views of the future, ideas or acts of self-harm or suicide, disturbed sleep, diminished appetite(5).

Relation between Diabetes and Depression:

Depression is a medical illness that causes feelings of sadness and often a loss of interest in activities you used to enjoy. It can get in the way of how well you function at work and home, including taking care of your diabetes. When you aren't able to manage your diabetes well, your risk goes up for diabetes complications like heart disease and nerve damage. People with diabetes are 2 to 3 times more likely to have depression than people without diabetes. Only 25% to 50% of people with diabetes who have depression get diagnosed and treated. But treatment therapy, medicine, or both is usually very effective. And without treatment, depression often gets worse, not better. The presence of depression and anxiety in diabetic patients worsens the prognosis of diabetes, increases the non-compliance to the medical treatment. There is a bidirectional association between diabetes and depression, a complex relation that might share biological mechanisms, whose understanding could provide a better treatment and improve the outcomes for these pathologies. Many new studies suggest that inflammatory responses are also involved in the pathophysiology of depression. Proinflammatory cytokines have been found to interact with many of the pathophysiological domains that characterize

depression, including neurotransmitter metabolism, neuroendocrine function, synaptic plasticity, and behaviour(6).

One possible explanation might be that the psychological burden of being ill may play an important role on triggering anxiety and depression. However, the fact that in patients with previously undiagnosed diabetes, depression had a higher prevalence and could be due to an unfavourable lifestyle, such as physical inactivity, unhealthy diet or a stressful lifestyle.

Severe hypoglycaemia in patients with DM2 and without anti-depressive treatment was positively associated with the severity of depressive symptoms, independent of glycaemic control, insulin therapy, lifestyle factors and diabetic complications(7).

A strong association between depression in patients in their forties with orally treated diabetes was found, compared to patients in their seventies(8). Both diabetes and depression reduce the quality of life for an individual, but together they have a more negative impact(9).

Diabetes care mainly consists of selfcare. Diabetes patients themselves have to regulate their blood glucose levels by monitoring their blood glucose levels and by balancing their food intake, physical activities and their intake of oral hypoglycaemic agents and/or insulin. The overall treatment goal is to prevent acute and chronic complications, while preserving a good quality of life. Several studies have shown that the quality of life in diabetes is decreased as compared to individuals without diabetes(10).

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Study type and location: The study was conducted among 100 type 2 diabetic patients at Bangalore Baptist Hospital, After taking consent from the reverent authorities, a face- to- face interview was conducted on 100 diabetic patients with PHQ-9 & MMAS-8 questionnaires along with demographic data, laboratory data and other relevant information about the patients were collected using data collection form. The collected data were analyzed based on gender, age group, years of managing diabetes, type of management and patients who were under dialysis and chemotherapy were excluded from the study and patient who doesn't want to take part in the study were excluded. Based on the severity of the disease, patients were educated on importance of management of diabetes, and maintaining a proper mental health, in PHQ-9 patients who scores >9 were considered to be depressed and in MMAS-8 patient who scores >2 were considered to be non-adherent. These results were analysed using chi-square test and to get the results. The purpose of the study was determine the psychological effects in patients managing diabetes and the factors behind it.

OBJECTIVES:

Primary objective:

- 1) To evaluate the prevalence of depression among patients with type 2 diabetes using the PHQ-9 (Patient Health Questionnaire-9).

Secondary objectives:

- 1) To assess the association between depression severity and demographic factors such as age, gender, marital status, income level, occupation, and area of residence (urban vs rural).
- 2) To examine the relationship between depression and clinical variables including duration of diabetes, presence of comorbidities, and glycemic control (HbA1C levels).
- 3) To determine the impact of medication adherence (measured using the MMAS-8 scale) on depression levels among diabetic patients.
- 4) To explore the influence of behavioral factors, including smoking and alcohol use, on the severity of depression in individuals with diabetes.

Inclusion criteria:

- Type 2 Diabetic patients
- Age above 18 years
- Patients who are willing to take part in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Non Diabetic patients
- Type 1 diabetic patients
- Patient undergoing Chemotherapy
- Patient undergo Dialysis
- Comatose patients

RESULTS:

A total of 100 type 2 diabetic patients were included in the study. Based on the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ), 61% of the participants had PHQ scores <9 (indicating minimal or no depression), while 39% had PHQ scores >9 (suggestive of clinically relevant depressive symptoms). The relationship between depressive symptoms and various demographic, socio-economic, behavioral, and clinical variables was evaluated.

Table 1. PHQ-9 severity distribution of 100 diabetic patients and scoring based on NDSS

PHQ-9 Score Range	Depression Severity	Number of Patients	Percentage
0-4	None to Minimal Depression	16	16%
5-9	Mild Depression	45	45%
10-27	Moderate to Severe Depression	39	39%

PHQ-9 Depression Severity

Fig 1. Pie chart showing the PHQ-9 depression severity distribution of diabetic patients

Out of 100 diabetic patients assessed using the PHQ-9 scale, a substantial proportion exhibited depressive symptoms. Based on standard PHQ-9 severity cut-off which set by the National Diabetes Service Scheme (NDSS) as mentioned below:

- 16% of participants had none to minimal depression (scores 0-4)
- 45% had mild depression (scores 5-9)
- 39% were found to have moderate to severe depression (scores 10-27)

These findings indicate that 84% of the study population exhibited at least mild depressive symptoms, with 39% requiring clinical attention or psychological intervention due to moderate to severe depression. The distribution suggests a significant burden of undiagnosed or untreated depression among diabetic patients.

Table 2. Sociodemographic profile of type 2 diabetes mellitus patients with or without depression

Variables	n=100	PHQ ≤ 9 n(%)	PHQ > 9 n(%)	X ² (p)
Age (Yrs)				
≤ 60	58	38 (65.6%)	20 (34.4%)	1.18 (p >0.05)
>60	42	23 (54.8%)	19 (45.2%)	
Gender				
Female	35	26 (74.3%)	9 (25.7%)	3.99 (0.04)
Male	65	35 (54.5%)	30 (45.5%)	
Education				
High school/Degree	68	40 (58.8%)	28 (41.2%)	0.29 (p >0.05)
Primary School / Secondary school	23	15 (65.2%)	8 (34.8%)	
Illiterates	9	6 (66.7%)	3 (33.3%)	
Occupation				
Regular	51	39 (76.5%)	12 (23.5%)	7.98 (0.004)
Retired /House Wife	25	14 (56.0%)	11 (44.0%)	
Daily wage skilled	24	8 (33.3%)	16 (66.7%)	
Monthly Income				
< 20,000	24	8 (33.3%)	16 (66.7%)	10.16 (0.001)
> 20,000	76	53 (69.8%)	23 (30.2%)	
Locality				
Rural	29	11 (38.0%)	18 (62.0%)	9.13 (0.002)
Urban	71	50 (70.4%)	21 (29.6%)	
Martial Status				
Married	80	53 (66.2%)	27 (32.8%)	4.63 (0.03)
Single/Widowed/Divorced	20	8 (40%)	12 (60%)	

Demographic Factors

- **Age:** Geriatric patients are slightly at risk of developing depression 19 out of 42 (i.e. 45.5%) and among non-geriatric patients 20 were found to be depressed. There is no significant difference in depression rates between younger (<60) and older (≥60) adults. Although slightly more older individuals reported depressive symptoms, the difference is not large enough to be statistically meaningful.
- **Gender:** In the current study involving 100 Diabetic patients, it was found that Male out of 65 patients 30 (45.5%) were found to be depressed and Female out of 35 patients
- 9 (29.4%) were found to be depressed, it shows Males in the sample show a significantly higher rate of depression compared to females. This finding contrasts with general trends in some populations where females may report higher depression, suggesting possible sociocultural or contextual factors influencing male mental health in this sample

Socio-Economic Variables:

- **Education Level:** Among 100 individuals 28 out of 68 having graduated /higher secondary education, 8 out of 23 individuals had a

primary/secondary level education and 3 out of 9 people didn't have minimal education, found to be depressed respectively. Educational attainment does not appear to significantly affect depression levels in this population. Depression was relatively evenly distributed across different education levels.

- **Occupation:** Among 24 daily wage people 16 were depressed and 12 out of 51 regular workers were depressed and 11 out of 25 people belong were house wife /retired people. Occupation has a strong relationship with depression. Daily wage earners have the highest depression rates, likely due to job insecurity, financial instability, or physically demanding work. In contrast, regularly employed individuals experience more stability and lower depression rates.
- **Monthly Income:** It was found out that, 30 out of 100 has low monthly income (less than 20,000) also 22 have scored PHQ > 9 and 70 out of 100 has an average monthly income (more than 20,000) also 30 have scored PHQ ≤ 9. Lower income is strongly associated with higher depression. Financial stress and reduced access to resources may contribute to this trend. Economic hardship is a clear risk factor for mental health issues in this group.
- **Locality:** Majority patients are from urban area

and 21 people among 71 were found to be depressed and remaining 29 people were from rural area and 18 were depressed so Rural populations are significantly more likely to experience depression than urban ones. Possible contributing factors include isolation, reduced access to healthcare, fewer employment opportunities, and stigma around mental health in rural areas.

- **Marital status:** It was found out that 80 out of 100 were married, 20 out of 100 were either

divorced or widowed and single. In that 27 out of 80 patients were found out to be married and depressed also, 16 out of 20 were found to be single, widowed or divorced. Married individuals tend to experience lower depression, possibly due to emotional and social support. Those who are single, widowed, or divorced show a higher risk, possibly linked to loneliness or lack of support systems.

Fig 2. Graph shows Avg. Depression Rate by Demographic & Socio-economic variables

- The highest average depression rate was observed among daily wage/skilled workers and individuals with income below ₹20,000, highlighting the impact of financial and job insecurity on mental health.
- Rural residents and those who were unmarried, widowed, or divorced also showed significantly higher depression rates, suggesting social and geographic vulnerability.

Table 3. Comparison of clinical profile and quality of life total and domain wise scores of Type 2 diabetes mellitus patients with or without depression

Variables	n=100	PHQ ≤ 9 n (%)	PHQ > 9 n (%)	X ² (P)
Social Habits				
Smoking/Drinking	44	20 (45.4%)	24 (54.6%)	5.14 (0.02)
Previously had but not now	18	11 (61.1%)	7 (39.9%)	
Nil Habits	38	30 (79.0%)	8 (21.0%)	
Duration of Diabetes (Years)				
<5	29	23 (79.3%)	6 (20.7%)	5.75 (0.01)
>5	71	38 (53.5%)	33 (46.5%)	
Diabetes Treatment				

Life Style Modification	15	11 (73.3%)	4 (26.7%)	2.12 ($p > 0.05$)
OHA	49	31 (63.2%)	18 (36.8%)	
Insulin	8	4 (50.0%)	4 (50.0%)	
OHA and Insulin	28	15 (53.5%)	13 (46.5%)	
Pill Burden (number of pills)				
<4	37	26 (70.2%)	11 (29.8%)	2.12 (0.14)
>4	63	35 (55.5%)	28 (44.5%)	
Medication Adherence				
High Adherence	20	16 (80.0%)	4 (11.2%)	9.26 (0.002)
Medium Adherence	35	26 (74.3%)	9 (25.7%)	
Poor Adherence	45	19 (42.3%)	26 (57.7%)	
Diabetic Control (HbA1C)				
6.9 % or less than	21	18 (85.7%)	3 (14.3%)	6.98 (0.008)
7.0 - 8.0	33	23 (69.6%)	10 (30.4%)	
8.0 <	46	20 (43.5%)	26 (56.5%)	
Comorbidities				
Yes	89	52 (58.4%)	37 (41.6%)	2.15 (0.133)
No	11	9 (81.8%)	2 (18.2%)	

Behavioral and Clinical Variables:

- **Social Habits:** A significant association was noted ($p = 0.02$). Patients currently using tobacco/alcohol had the highest depression rates (54.6%), whereas those with no such habits had the lowest (21.0%).
- **Duration of Diabetes:** A significant relationship was observed ($p = 0.01$). Patients with diabetes for more than 5 years had a higher depression rate (46.5%) than those with disease duration under 5 years (20.7%).
- **Type of Diabetes Treatment:** No statistically significant association was found between treatment modality and depression ($p = 0.54$). However, The depression rate was highest among those on insulin alone (50%) and those on combined therapy (46.5%), and lowest in those managed by lifestyle changes (26.7%). More intensive or complex regimens, such as insulin or polytherapy, may reflect more advanced disease, which can be psychologically burdensome.
- **Pill Burden:** No significant association was noted ($p = 0.14$), although patients taking more than four pills per day had higher depression prevalence (44.5%) than those taking fewer (29.8%).
- **Medication Adherence:** A strong, statistically significant association was found between medication adherence and depression ($\chi^2 = 9.26$, $p = 0.002$). Depression was seen in only (11.2%) of patients with high adherence, compared to (57.7%) among those with poor adherence. Poor adherence could be both a cause and consequence of depression. Depression may impair motivation and memory, reducing adherence, while nonadherence may lead to worsening glycemic control and psychological distress.
- **Glycemic Control (HbA1C):** A strong association was found ($p = 0.008$). Depression was most common among those with HbA1C > 8.0% (56.5%) and least common in those with HbA1C \leq 6.9% (14.3%).
- **Comorbidities:** Though not statistically significant ($p = 0.133$), depression was more frequent in patients with comorbid conditions (41.6%) compared to those without (18.2%).

Fig 2. Graph shows Avg. Depression Rate by Behavioral & Clinical Variables

- Clinical complexity contributed heavily to depression, especially in patients with poor glycemic control (HbA1C > 8.0%), poor medication adherence, and comorbid conditions.
- Higher depression rates were observed in those using insulin, taking more than four pills daily, with longer diabetes duration, or current/former substance use indicating the burden of intensive disease management.

DISCUSSION:

Summary of the study:

This study investigates the prevalence of depression among type 2 diabetic patients and its association with various demographic, socio-economic, behavioral, and clinical parameters. The findings reveal a considerable burden of depression in this population, emphasizing the need for routine psychological assessment as part of diabetes management, especially in resource-limited healthcare settings.

Age and gender emerged as relevant demographic factors. Although age showed no significant association ($p > 0.05$), a higher proportion of patients aged over 60 years exhibited depressive symptoms (45.2%) compared to younger individuals (34.4%). Notably, gender differences were statistically significant ($p = 0.04$), with females demonstrating a lower rate of depression (25.7%) than males (45.5%), suggesting possible variations in health-seeking behavior, social support, or coping mechanisms.

In terms of socio-economic status, individuals with monthly income below ₹20,000 experienced significantly higher depression rates (66.7%) compared to those earning more (30.2%) ($p = 0.001$).

This aligns with global evidence linking financial stress to mental health disorders. Occupation also significantly influenced depression prevalence ($p = 0.004$), with the highest rate among daily wage/skilled workers (66.7%), reflecting the psychological toll of job instability and physical strain. Furthermore, rural residents reported higher depression rates (62.0%) compared to their urban counterparts (29.6%) ($p = 0.002$), potentially due to limited healthcare access, social isolation, and fewer educational or employment opportunities. Similarly, marital status was a significant factor ($p = 0.03$), with unmarried, widowed, or divorced individuals exhibiting a higher prevalence of depression (60%) than married individuals (32.8%), underscoring the protective role of family and social support.

Regarding behavioral and clinical characteristics, individuals with a history of smoking or alcohol consumption showed significantly elevated depression levels (54.6%, $p = 0.02$), whereas those without such habits had a notably lower rate (21%). This indicates that substance use remains a major modifiable risk factor for mental health disturbances in diabetic populations.

A strong association was also found with duration of diabetes ($p = 0.01$), where patients living with the disease for more than five years had a depression prevalence of 46.5%, compared to only 20.7% among those with shorter disease duration. Although treatment modality (lifestyle, oral agents, insulin, or combination therapy) did not show a significant statistical relationship ($p = 0.54$), patients requiring insulin or combination therapy showed higher depression rates, possibly reflecting greater disease burden or perceived treatment complexity.

Pill burden, although not statistically significant ($p = 0.14$), followed a similar trend, with patients taking more than four pills daily experiencing higher depression rates (44.5%) than those with a lower burden (29.8%). Importantly, medication adherence showed a significant relationship with depression ($p = 0.002$). Poor adherence was associated with the highest depression rate (57.7%), compared to medium (25.7%) and high adherence (11.2%). This reflects a bi-directional interaction: depression may reduce adherence due to poor motivation or cognitive impairment, while suboptimal adherence may worsen clinical outcomes, further contributing to psychological distress.

Glycemic control (HbA1C levels) was also significantly associated with depression ($p = 0.008$). Patients with HbA1C levels $>8.0\%$ had the highest prevalence of depression (56.5%), while those with well-controlled diabetes ($<6.9\%$) had a much lower rate (14.3%). These findings reinforce the interconnectedness between metabolic and mental health, where poor glycemic control may lead to inflammatory and neuroendocrine changes that influence mood.

Although comorbidities did not reach statistical significance in this dataset ($p = 0.133$), patients with additional health conditions still demonstrated a higher depression rate (41.6%) compared to those without (18.2%), suggesting a trend worthy of further investigation in larger cohorts.

In summary, the study establishes that depression in diabetic patients is influenced by a variety of demographic, economic, behavioral, and clinical factors. High-risk groups identified include males, low-income earners, rural residents, single/widowed individuals, those with a longer duration of diabetes, poor adherence to medication, and poor glycemic control. These insights highlight the critical need for integrating mental health evaluation and support into diabetes care protocols. Early identification and multidisciplinary intervention strategies could significantly improve both psychological well-being and clinical outcomes in this vulnerable population.

Comaprison with previous studies:

Gupta et al. (2020) conducted a cross-sectional study of 300 diabetic patients in rural North India, using the PHQ-9 and a Hindi-translated Quality of Life

Instrument to evaluate the impact of depression on diabetes management and its association with treatment complexity. The study reported a 25.6% prevalence of clinical depression, with predictors including illiteracy, impaired emotional/mental health, and role limitations due to diabetes. While the study did not directly analyze the relationship between specific antidiabetic medications (such as insulin vs. oral agents) and the presence of depression, it highlighted that patients with depressive symptoms were more likely to have poor medication adherence and worse glycemic control factors often indicative of the burden of complex regimens(11).

A notable cross-sectional study by Anugraha et al. (2023) conducted at a tertiary care center in Tamil Nadu, India, involved 114 T2DM patients. It reported a 22.8% prevalence of depression (PHQ-9 ≥ 10), confirmed using the Mini-International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI). Among these, 15.8% had mild and 7% had moderate depression. The study identified female gender, poor glycemic control (HbA1c $\geq 8\%$), and comorbid systemic hypertension as independent predictors of depression(12).

A landmark meta-analysis by Yu et al. (2015), which included over 2.4 million individuals across 42 studies, concluded that depression is associated with a 32% increased risk of developing type 2 diabetes (RR = 1.32, 95% CI: 1.28–1.37). This finding highlights not only the psychological burden among diabetic individuals but also implicates depression as a risk factor for incident diabetes. The study suggested both behavioral (e.g., physical inactivity, poor diet) and biological mechanisms (e.g., inflammation, HPA axis dysregulation) as mediators of this relationship(13).

Similarly, Anderson et al. (2001) previously reported that the prevalence of depression in diabetic patients was nearly twice that of the general population, with pooled prevalence rates of 31% for clinically significant depressive symptoms(14). Another systematic review by Roy and Lloyd (2012) confirmed this association, identifying a median depression prevalence of 19.1% in T2DM populations globally(15).

In a cross-sectional study of 400 patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) in Ghana, Akpalu et al. (2018) assessed depressive symptoms using the PHQ-9 and measured glycemic control via HbA1c levels. The study found a high prevalence of depression at 31.3%. Initially, poor glycemic control (HbA1c $\geq 7\%$) was significantly associated with increased odds of depression (OR = 1.82, $p < 0.001$) in unadjusted analyses. However, this association became non-significant in fully adjusted multivariate models that accounted for clinical confounders such as insulin therapy, comorbidities, and demographic factors (adjusted OR = 1.04, $p = 0.286$). These findings suggest that while poor glycemic control may initially correlate with depression in T2DM patients in this setting, its effect appears to be attenuated by broader

clinical and psychosocial factors when modeled comprehensively(16).

LIMITATIONS:

Cross-Sectional Design:

The study design limits the ability to establish causal relationships between depression and the associated demographic or clinical variables.

Small Sample Size:

With only 100 participants, the statistical power may be limited, and the findings may not be generalizable to larger or more diverse diabetic populations.

Single-Center Study:

Conducted at Bangalore Baptist Hospital, the results may reflect regional or institutional patterns and may not apply to other geographic or healthcare settings.

Self-Reported Measures:

Depression (PHQ-9), medication adherence (MMAS-8), and lifestyle factors like smoking or alcohol use were assessed through self-report, which may introduce reporting bias or social desirability bias.

Lack of Longitudinal Follow-Up:

The study does not evaluate changes in depression or diabetic control over time, missing potential temporal trends or the effect of interventions.

Unmeasured Confounders:

Variables such as family support, stress levels, type of diabetes, or access to healthcare were not evaluated and could influence both depression and diabetes outcomes.

Exclusion of Severe Mental Illnesses:

Patients with diagnosed psychiatric disorders may have been excluded or underrepresented, potentially underestimating the true burden of depression.

CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS:

Routine Depression Screening Should be Standard in Diabetes Care:

Given the high prevalence of undiagnosed depression (39% with PHQ > 9), especially among long-standing diabetics, integrating tools like the PHQ-9 into regular diabetic check-ups is essential.

Early Identification of High-Risk Groups:

Males, rural residents, low-income earners, daily wage workers, and individuals with poor medication adherence or poor glycemic control should be prioritized for mental health evaluation.

Addressing Psychological Barriers to Medication Adherence:

Since poor adherence was strongly linked to depression, treating depression may improve

adherence and, in turn, enhance diabetes outcomes.

Glycemic Control Should Include Mental Health Monitoring:

Poor HbA1C control was significantly associated with depression. This highlights that uncontrolled blood sugar levels may be both a cause and a consequence of depression, requiring a dual-targeted approach.

Behavioral Counseling and Lifestyle Interventions are Needed:

Smoking and alcohol use were associated with higher depression rates. Lifestyle counseling should include psychological and addiction support for diabetic patients.

Multidisciplinary Care Approach is Essential:

Involving psychologists, diabetes educators, and social workers in routine care can address both the metabolic and emotional needs of the patient.

Mental Health Awareness and Education in Rural Areas:

Since rural populations showed higher depression rates, community-based mental health awareness programs should be expanded in underserved areas.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS:

Longitudinal Studies to Assess Causality:

Future research should employ prospective or longitudinal designs to establish causal relationships between depression and diabetes-related outcomes such as glycemic control, complications, and treatment adherence.

Larger, Multi-Centric Studies:

Conducting studies with larger and more diverse populations across multiple centers will enhance the generalizability of the findings and reflect broader sociodemographic variations.

Interventional Trials:

There is a need for randomized controlled trials (RCTs) to evaluate the impact of integrated mental health interventions such as cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), counseling, or support groups on depression and diabetic outcomes.

Qualitative Research on Patient Perspectives:

Exploring patients lived experiences through qualitative interviews can provide deeper insight into the psychosocial burdens of living with diabetes and how they relate to depressive symptoms.

Digital Health and Telepsychiatry Integration:

Future studies should assess the feasibility and effectiveness of telemedicine, mobile health apps, and digital mental health tools for screening and managing

depression in diabetic populations.

Exploring Additional Psychosocial Variables:

Future research should include variables such as stress levels, family/social support, sleep patterns, and self-efficacy to build a more holistic model of depression risk in diabetes.

Focus on Youth and Newly Diagnosed Patients:

Depression in adolescents and newly diagnosed diabetics is under-researched. Early identification in these subgroups may help prevent chronic mental health issues.

CONCLUSION:

This study highlights a significant burden of depression among diabetic patients, with 39% experiencing moderate to severe depressive symptoms. Key demographic factors such as male gender, low income, rural residence, unmarried status, and daily wage employment were found to be significantly associated with higher PHQ-9 scores. Clinically, longer duration of diabetes, poor glycemic control (HbA1C > 8.0%), poor medication adherence, and substance use (smoking/alcohol) were strongly linked with depression. These findings underscore the multidimensional nature of depression in diabetes and reinforce the importance of incorporating routine mental health screening into diabetic care. Addressing psychosocial and behavioral determinants alongside medical management is essential for improving both mental health and metabolic outcomes. Early identification and intervention, especially among high-risk groups, can play a critical role in enhancing quality of life and long-term disease control in patients with diabetes.

DECLARATIONS:

Abbreviations:

- **T2DM-** TYPE 2 Diabetes Mellitus
- **PHQ-** Patient Health Questionnaire
- **MMAS-** Morisky Medication Adherence Scale
- **MDD-** Major Depressive Disorder
- **NDSS-** National Diabetes Service Scheme
- **HbA1c-** Glycosylated Haemoglobin
- **OHA-** Oral Hyperglycaemic Agents
- **WHO-** World Health Organisation
- **IDF-** International Diabetes Federation
- **MODY-** Maturity-onset diabetes of the young
- **DIS-** Diagnostic Interview Schedule
- **BMI-** Body Mass Index
- **FBS-** Fasting Blood Sugar
- **MEPS-** Medical Expenditure Panel Survey
- **RCT-** Randomized Controlled Trials

- **CBT-** Cognitive Behavioral Therapy

Ethics approval and consent to participate:

Given the strictly observational nature of the study, which entailed no interventions, modification to treatment protocol or alteration in clinical management. Ethical approval was deemed unnecessary, as the study did not pose any potential risk or impact on the standard care provided to the subjects. This study did not involve participant consent, as it is an observational study.

Conflict of interest:

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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